

OSPARK Research Protocol Appendix 2: Study 1 Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form

Title of study: Open Science Promotion and Advocacy for Research Knowledge (OSPARK)
Study 1: Qualitative investigation of needs and barriers.

Thank you for your interest in taking part in this study. Before you decide whether to participate, it is important that you understand why this research is being conducted and what it will involve. Please take the time to read the following information carefully. You may discuss it with others if needed.

Please contact us if you have any questions or need further information. Our contact details are further down the page.

This content is adapted with permission from [participant information sheet and consent form templates](#) developed by the Research Governance, Ethics and Integrity Team at Queen's University Belfast.

Quick summary

- This study is being organised by researchers from OLS (Open Life Science Limited) and DRA (DRA Digital Research Academy GmbH).
- We are aiming to identify the outreach, marketing, and communications activities that open science advocates take part in; the barriers they experience regarding these activities; and their needs and preferences regarding training in these topics.
- As part of this study, you will be asked to take part in a workshop with a teaching component and a facilitated discussion component. Recordings and notes of the discussion will be used for analysis. You can also upload any notes you take personally during the session, but this is optional.
- Your data will be stored on an internal Google Drive, accessible only to the [OLS](#) and [DRA](#) teams, until data analysis begins. Your data will be stored in compliance with UK data protection legislation. Data will be anonymised before analysis and all personally identifiable information will be deleted when the study concludes. Anonymised data will be shared on an openly accessible GitHub and/or Zenodo repository.

- This study is part of the Open Science Promotion and Advocacy for Research Knowledge (OSPARK) Bootcamp, funded by the first OSCARS Open Call. The OSCARS project has received funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101129751.

What is the purpose of the study?

This study aims to understand how open science advocates engage in outreach activities, and what barriers prevent them from doing so. It also aims to identify what training open science advocates feel they need in marketing, communications, and outreach activities. This is a qualitative study which aims to capture the experiences, barriers, and training needs of open science advocates in their own words.

Who can take part?

This study is being conducted in conjunction with workshops and training pilots. You have been invited to take part as an attendee. We are seeking responses from anyone who attends an OSPARK workshop or training pilot. We expect this will mainly be researchers, research professionals, or students who are engaged in open science. Our expectation is that 15-50 people will participate in this study.

What will happen to me if I take part?

This study will involve taking part in a workshop or longer training pilot of OSPARK training material. This will initially involve joining a training session in which we will use resources from the OSPARK training programme to introduce you to key concepts in outreach, marketing, and communications for open science. You may also be provided a workbook to help you apply this knowledge. You do not need to take part in the study to join this section of the workshop.

If you have provided informed consent, you will then take part in discussion groups to identify your experiences of open science outreach activities, your barriers to participating in these activities, and your training needs in relation to these activities. There will be 2-10 people in your group. Your group will be provided a Google Doc with instructions and a template for note-taking, including a semi-structured list of questions. The discussion will be recorded, if this is feasible. Both the recording and the collective notes will be used in data analysis. You will optionally be able to submit any documents you created during the training segment to supplement our analysis.

Information about logistics, such as how long the workshop will run for, will be provided in a presentation at the beginning of the workshop. There may have been an agenda provided

which will also contain this information.

What will happen to my data?

This research will be conducted in compliance with data protection legislation. Your data will be stored and managed by OLS (Open Life Science Limited), a UK based social enterprise. By taking part in this study, you are expected to abide by the [Chatham House Rule](#):

When a meeting, or part thereof, is held under the Chatham House Rule, participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed.

As part of this study, we will be collecting the following data:

- Your response to the consent form on this page.
- Recordings of the group discussions.
- Any collective notes made during group discussions.
- Any documents which are optionally submitted.

Your consent form response will be stored separately from the recordings, collective notes, and documents. This will be kept by OLS and DRA on a closed Google Drive folder until analysis is completed and shared. At this point, your consent form responses will be deleted. Only OLS and DRA employees will have access to this data.

During the workshop, collective notes will be taken on a shared Google Doc. The link will only be shared with workshop attendees, as well as OLS and DRA team members. Please note that the Google Doc will have open editing permissions, so may be accessible by third parties, if the link is shared beyond the intended participants. As a participant, you will be asked to confirm that you will not share this link to anyone outside of the workshop. The document will be changed to closed access (that is, only accessible to the OLS and DRA teams) within 48 hours of the workshop concluding.

Recordings, collective notes, and submitted documents may contain identifiable information. These will be stored on a closed Google Drive folder and anonymised prior to analysis beginning. Only OLS and DRA will have access to the data before it is anonymised.

This study has been designed according to open science principles. Anonymised data will therefore be shared publicly under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International \(CC-BY\)](#) license, unless deemed to be a risk to participant safety or wellbeing.

Our full data management plan [<add link when available>](#) is publicly accessible.

What are the possible benefits, risks, or disadvantages of taking part?

The benefits of taking part in this study include taking part in the training session for free, which may require a fee at a later date; and having the opportunity to shape training on outreach, marketing, and communications for open science initiatives.

There is a risk that your responses may be identifiable, even after anonymisation, given the open data policy of this study. There is also a risk that other participants may share identifiable information about the discussion with others, although we expect that agreeing to the Chatham House Rule mitigates this.

What if something goes wrong?

If you have any concerns about any aspects of the study, you should contact the lead researcher:

Bethan Iley
OSPARK Coordinator & Finance Manager
bethan@we-are-ols.org

Should you remain unhappy with the response and wish to make a formal complaint, please make a report under OLS's [Code of Conduct policy](#).

What will happen to the results of the research?

Upon conclusion of this study, the findings may be written into a scientific journal article and presented at scientific conferences. This is to share our results with other researchers in the field. You can get updated about the findings of this research by signing up to the [OSPARK mailing list](#).

The anonymous data from this study will be shared publicly under a [Creative Commons Attribution \(CC-BY\) 4.0 International license](#). This means that other researchers may use the data to verify our results or conduct their own research in the future.

Who is organising and funding the research?

This study is led by a team of researchers at OLS (Open Life Science Limited) and DRA (DRA Digital Research Academy GmbH). OLS is a non-profit company limited by guarantee, based

in the United Kingdom (company number [12824090](#)). DRA is a grassroots trainer network based in Germany (HRB 295646).

The research team for this study consists of the following people:

- Bethan Iley, OSPARK Coordinator & Finance Manager, OLS
- Heidi Seibold, Co-Executive Director, DRA
- Joyce Kao, Co-Executive Director, DRA
- Yo Yehudi, Co-Executive Director, OLS

The development of this research project was also supported by the following people:

- Deborah Udoh, Open Life Science Ltd, United Kingdom/Nigeria
- Riva Quiroga, Open Life Science Ltd, United Kingdom/Chile

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Who has reviewed the study?

This study has been reviewed by *<name of research ethics committee or IRB>*. If you have any questions or concerns about the ethics review for this study, you can contact them at *<IRB email>* using reference *<reference number>*.

Contact for Further Information

If you have questions or comments about the study, please contact the lead researcher on this study:

Bethan Iley
OSPARK Coordinator & Finance Manager
bethan@we-are-ols.org

If your questions or concerns remain unresolved, please contact the Principle Investigator:

Yo Yehudi
Executive Director
yo@we-are-ols.org

Thank you for your interest in this study and for taking the time to read through this information page.

By indicating that you consent to taking part in the research on our event sign-up page, you are agreeing to the following statements:

- I confirm that I have read, or had read to me, and understand the information presented above about this study. I have had the opportunity to ask questions and these have been answered fully.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason and without my legal rights being affected.
- I understand the study is being conducted by researchers from Open Life Science Limited and that my personal information will be held and handled in compliance with data protection legislation.
- I understand that data collected as part of this will be accessible to employees and contractors at Open Life Science Limited (also known as OLS) and DRA Digital Research Academy GmbH (also known as DRA). I give permission for these individuals to have access to this information.
- I understand that the information I provide may be published as a report. Confidentiality and anonymity will be maintained and it will not be possible to identify me from any publications.
- As a participant in a group discussion, I agree to abide by the Chatham House Rule: that I am free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed.
- I understand that there are limits to confidentiality, as revelations that are criminal or which suggest a risk of physical harm may require confidentiality to be broken by the researchers.
- I understand the discussion group will be digitally recorded and there is a possibility of anonymised quotations being used in publications.
- I agree that any anonymised notes and transcripts that I contribute to can be deposited in GitHub and/or Zenodo to promote transparency and public accessibility to research.
- I agree to take part in the above study.

Note. An explicit consent checkbox will be provided as part of the online registration form for the workshop event.

